
SPECIFIC FEATURES OF LANGUAGE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CULTURE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7353385>

Juraeva Zamira Kuchkarboevna

Teacher of English at the Department of Foreign Languages
Ferghana Branch of the Tashkent University
of Information technologies

ABSTRACT

This article is dedicated to the actual questions of developing process of languages. Language and culture are closely interconnected and the development of mankind have shown that the language could not be exist without culture.

Keywords: languages, culture, inheritance, heritage, mentality.

There are many ways to express our feelings. By gestures...like a primitive people in stone era or dumb people nowadays, by some noises or sounds or at last, we may actually draw what we want to say. However, the universal method to communicate is decided as ‘language’. Surely, the humanity passed a long way in order to not only express our feelings or thoughts, but also to realize it in real life. Poets convey their minds by their poems, stories, novels Artists via their portraits, paintings, and film-directors via their cinemas, films, cartoons. And there is a long list of specialists, who dedicate their life to express, to discover themselves in their works. Let to mention that the fundamental basic maintain object, or heart of all that is being for sure, the language. “Why the language?” you may ask, if there are many steps of evolution of humanity as actually known by humankind. It may be work, labor, need of food, and of course the Mother Nature. All those are being facts of history, a true reasons formation of human beings. Nevertheless, let us think deeply or mentally, what is another no less than important stage of developing...undoubtedly – the human brain. The brain has pushed up us to think, to work, to secure our homes, to hunt, to gather, to help each other and vice versa to fight, to travel, to cook, to live...to exist in life. And what the brain gifted us? Reproduced a vitally important product - the language, and the language reproduced the culture. Both of it tied up each other.

The relationship between language and culture is deeply rooted. Language is used to maintain and convey culture and cultural ties. Different ideas stem from differing language use within one's culture and the whole intertwining of these relationships start at one's birth.

When an infant is born, it is not unlike any other infant born, in fact, quite similar. It is not until the child is exposed to their surroundings that they become individuals in and of their cultural group. This idea, which describes all people as similar at birth, has been around for thousands of years and was discussed by Confucius as recorded in the book by his followers, Analects.

Culture is the product of language. In order to clarify both of these notions I pleased to turn to the coherent explanation of Clifford Geertz that:

- 1) Culture is a kind of social inheritance instead of biological heritage;
- 2) Culture is shared by the whole community, not belonging to any particular individual;
- 3) Culture is a symbolic meaning system in which language is one of the most important ones;
- 4) Culture is a unified system, the integral parts of which are closely related to one another.

David Krech explained the major functions of language from the following three aspects:

- 1) Language is the primary vehicle of communication;
- 2) Language reflects both the personality of the individual and the culture of his history. In turn, it helps shape both personality and culture;
- 3) Language makes possible the growth and transmission of culture, the continuity of societies, and the effective functioning and control of social group.

The understanding of a culture and its people can be enhanced by the knowledge of their language.

Different languages will create different limitations, therefore a people who share a culture but speak different languages, will have different world views. Still, language is rooted in culture and culture is reflected and passed on by language from one generation to the next.

From this, one can see that learning a new language involves the learning of a new culture. Consequently, teachers of a language are also teachers of culture.

Language – the way we speak and culture - the way we think.

As being a limited frame of thinking, culture began to emerge from time immemorial. Distinctive feature in the development of culture as an integral part of our lives become territorial division. It contributed to the comprehensive development of mankind, or rather two sides of the world or two continents, existing apart from and to some extent complementing to each other – East and West.

Of course, this division has served to bilateral development of mankind. Let me reveal a few facts, which can be considered as the difference between Eastern and Western cultural development of society, and to get started let's find out why they differ from one another.

The primary source of civilization course is considered the East. This is an ancient Egypt, Ancient Mesopotamia Ancient China and etc. In the east has always been the state control the Supreme Head- Emperor, who regulated public relations between citizens. And why was necessary to control? To unite the people and direct them in the right direction, namely, collaborative teamwork, for irrigation because in the east has always been a shortage of water. The construction of irrigation canals, holding collective workers khashars led people to work together and united.

On the other hand in the west were observed individual personal development work. For example, a farmer planted a tree, it gave the harvest surpluses were formed, he goes on to sell these surpluses on the market and got a profit, thus the different segments of the population are placed. As every family and every land fertility is different. That means a bilateral economic development also affects to the cultural development.

For the beginning of comparison, it is important to say: "East is the cradle of the traditions, customs and national spirit", because East has not lost its elegance individuality and identity. In ancient times, in the days of the Great Silk Road had just begun its activity when there was an exchanging of goods, culture and the spreading of religion, humanity in the East got new civil character, whereas in the west prevailed struggle for freedom, justice, and for the land.

Today when we talk about Europe, we imagine the rapid development of the economy, a strong stable policy, the peak of science and techniques. Unfortunately referred to these categories we doubt to add the spiritual development of the nation to what included in all the components of cultural development, namely national dishes, clothes national holidays in Europe now acquired modern meaning, for example such as Halloween, Thanksgiving Day, Carnival in Brazil do not belong in the category of national holidays, compared to cite a number of Eastern events such

as our national holiday of Navruz, Chunzhie in China, Sonnali in Korea, holiday Holly in India celebrated in a large scale. People in these days are genuinely happy, gather in large companies, visit the older generation, dressed in national costumes prepare the most exquisite national dishes

Another notable aspect of culture is its effect on the mentality of the people.

We, Asians, respect and venerate of the older generation and it's generally accepted as a measure of commitment or breeding rights. For example, the majority of the eastern nations in speaking there is a special respectful form of address and official welcome seniors, such as Koreans and Japanese have separate official- polite speech styles. Welcome concomitant special gestures: Koreans tilt, the Uzbeks keep a hand on breast and Indians even kiss the feet of elders.

Another measure of respect for elders is manifested in a manner to behave in public places and transport giving a place to seniors, pregnant women, and people with disabilities is one of the rules of etiquette, which we are taught from an early years. Whereas in Europe giving a place for senior is like humiliation and underestimation of physical abilities elders. Parents– main members of the family, ensuring parents in financial and spiritual care, supporting and cohabitation is reciprocal gratitude children, which is fixed by state law. Whereas in Europe living with parents of children full age is being a humiliation teasing the child as an harmoniously undeveloped not an independent figure, who did not find their place in society.

In conclusion it is necessary to emphasize that humanity and the people, how they were not different, to what nation they would not be treated, no matter how different cultures and mentality mankind has made a new general step into the new century, showing tolerance and patience to each other.

It is impossible for one to teach language without teaching culture. The implications for language teaching and policy making are therefore vast and far reaching. As a teacher of language, one must be culturally aware, considerate of the students` culture, and inform students of cultural differences thus promoting understanding. Language policy must reflect both the target language culture as well as the students`, teacher`s, and administrative persons` culture thus avoiding any cultural misinterpretations.

REFERENCES

1. Allwright D., Bailey K. M. Focus on the language classroom: an introduction to classroom research for language teachers. – Cambridge. Cambridge University Press, 1991.
2. Byram M. Cultural studies in foreign language education. – Clevedon. Multilingual Matters, 1989.
3. Emmitt M., Pollock J. Language and learning: an introduction for teaching (2nded). – Melbourne. Oxford University Press, 1997.
4. Geertz C. The Interpretation of cultures. – Basic Books, 1973.
5. Krech D. Individual in Society: a textbook of social psychology. – McGraw-Hill, 1962.
6. Xu Z.G. Interpretation of Analects. – Beijing. People’s Literature Press, 1997.